

Simultaneous Adsorption of Ions from Solution. Part I. Adsorption of Metal Ions by Hydrated Manganese Dioxide.

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A certain amount of work has been done on the simultaneous adsorption of two solutes from solution by adsorbents. Thus Masius ("Uber die Adsorption in Gemischen," *Dissertation*, Leipzig, 1908) studied the simultaneous adsorption of mixtures of organic acids by blood charcoal and arrived at the conclusion that less of each was adsorbed than if the other was not present. A similar result was also obtained by Freundlich and Poser (*Kolloid-Chem. Beih.* 1914, 6, 499) with mixtures of organic acids and alumina. Schmidt (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1910, 74, 730) also found a similar result in the adsorption of iodine and acetic acid by charcoal. Other works in this line are those of Lachs and Michaelis (*Zeit. Elektrochem.*, 1911, 17, 1), Freundlich and Kaempfer (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1915, 90, 681), Rona and Michaelis (*Biochem. Zeit.*, 1909, 16, 499); Bancroft ("Applied Colloid Chemistry", 1921, 113) has summarised the main work in this direction.

The work described in this paper was undertaken to throw some light on the phenomenon of antagonistic action of ions in the coagulation of colloids, specially in relation to the so-called displacement of adsorption of one ion in the presence of another adsorbable ion of the same charge, a point on which Weiser (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1921, 25, 399; 1924, 28, 232) in some recent papers has

laid much stress. According to him the antagonistic action of two electrolytes is, in the main, due to the fact that the presence of one coagulating ion in some cases cuts down the adsorption of the other and hence stabilises the sol towards that coagulating ion. It was, however, shown by one of us (*cf.* Sen, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 536) that this fact alone would not be enough to cause the antagonistic action. Though the adsorption of each is separately diminished, the total adsorption of both the ions may be equivalent to the adsorption of either of coagulating ions when only one is present at the coagulating concentration. Since the coagulation of a colloid depends primarily upon a decrease in the effective charge on the colloid particles, equivalent amounts of different ions are necessary for it. Hence when the sum total of the adsorption of the ions separately expressed in electro-chemical equivalents reaches a certain limit, the colloid will be coagulated irrespective of whether the original point of adsorption of one ion when present alone to coagulate the sol has been reached or not. In order to support the explanation of Weiser it is necessary to show that though one of the ions is not appreciably adsorbed, simply by its presence the adsorption of a second ion is diminished considerably. This effect would then be similar to the so-called "poisoning" of catalysts. It was felt that the existing data on adsorption including those of Weiser are inadequate for a proper study of this subject because in no case a simultaneous measurement of the adsorption of both the coagulating ions has been made. Thus Weiser (*loc. cit.*), in the coagulation of arsenious sulphide sol by a mixture of lithium and barium salts, observed that the adsorption of barium ion is cut down by the presence of lithium but he did not determine the amount of adsorption of the lithium ion at the same time.

In this paper we have given the results of the simultaneous adsorption of several metallic ion pairs by hydrated manganese dioxide. We have used a precipitated sample instead of a sol because it has been found that the precipitated oxide can be obtained in a much purer state than the colloid and secondly, the results in both the cases are similar, varying only in the absolute amount of adsorption.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The hydrated manganese dioxide was prepared by the Volhard's reaction in presence of strong potassium nitrate solution, washed free from electrolytes and then air dried. Two grams of the same preparation have been used in each experiment, the total volume of the solution being always 50 c.c. The mixtures examined are $\text{BaCl}_2 + \text{CuCl}_2$, $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + \text{AgNO}_3$, $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + \text{KNO}_3$, $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + \text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$, and $\text{AgNO}_3 + \text{KNO}_3$. Copper was estimated volumetrically by means of thiosulphate, and silver, by means of thiocyanate; barium and potassium gravimetrically as sulphates and aluminium as oxide. The time allowed for adsorption to take place was twenty hours though it was found that equilibrium was reached much earlier.

TABLE I.

Adsorption of Copper from $\text{CuCl}_2 + \text{BaCl}_2$.

Original concentration of Cu^{++} in milli-equivalents.	Adsorption of Cu^{++} in milli-equivalents.			
	$\text{Ba}^{++} = 0$	$\text{Ba}^{++} = 10$ milli-equivalent.	$\text{Ba}^{++} = 15$ milli-equivalent.	$\text{Ba}^{++} = 20$ milli-equivalent.
24·32	2·42	1·92
18·24	2·24	1·89	1·79	1·64
12·16	1·96	1·76	1·56	1·26
6·08	1·65	1·48	1·33	1·08

TABLE II.

Adsorption of Ba⁺⁺ from BaCl₂ + CuCl₂.

Original concentration of Ba ⁺⁺ in milli-equivalents	Adsorption of Ba ⁺⁺ in milli-equivalents.				
	Cu ⁺⁺ = 0	Cu ⁺⁺ = 6.08 milli-equiv.	Cu ⁺⁺ = 12.16 milli-equiv.	Cu ⁺⁺ = 18.24 milli-equiv.	Cu ⁺⁺ = 24.32 milli-equiv.
20	1.366	1.238	1.058	0.955	...
15	1.255	0.724	...
10	1.109	0.865	0.724	0.659	0.484
5	0.827

TABLE III.

*Adsorption of Ag⁺ from AgNO₃ + Ba(NO₃)₂
and AgNO₃ + KNO₃.*

Original concentration of Ag ⁺ in grams.	Adsorption of Ag ⁺ in grams.				
	Ba ⁺⁺ = 0 K ⁺ = 0	Ba ⁺⁺ = 0.3434 gm.	Ba ⁺⁺ = 1.0363 gm.	K ⁺ = 0.391 gm.	K ⁺ = 0.5865 gm.
2.1596	0.4413	0.4413
1.6197	0.3922	0.3922	0.3922
1.0798	0.3360	0.3360	0.3360	0.3360	...
0.5399	0.2581	0.2581	0.2574

TABLE IV.

*Adsorption of Ba⁺⁺ from Ba(NO₃)₂ + KNO₃
Ba(NO₃)₂ + Al(NO₃)₃.*

Original concentration of Ba ⁺⁺ in milli-equivalents.	Adsorption of Ba ⁺⁺ in milli-equivalents.			
	K ⁺ = 0 Al ⁺⁺⁺ = 0	K ⁺ = 10 milli-equivalent.	K ⁺ = 15 milli-equivalent.	Al ⁺⁺⁺ = 14.61 milli-equivalent.
20	1.43
15	1.40	...	0.92	1.32
10	1.126	0.99
5	0.952

TABLE V.

Adsorption of Al⁺⁺⁺ from Al(NO₃)₃ + Ba(NO₃)₂.

Original concentration of Al ⁺⁺⁺ in milli-equivalents.	Adsorption of Al ⁺⁺⁺ in milli-equivalents.	
	Ba ⁺⁺ = 0	Ba ⁺⁺ = 15 milli-equivalent.
14.61	1.44	1.027

TABLE VI.

Adsorption of K⁺ from KNO₃ + Ba(NO₃)₂.

Original concentration of K ⁺ in milli-equivalents.	Adsorption of K ⁺ in milli-equivalents.	
	Ba ⁺⁺ = 0	Ba ⁺⁺ = 10 milli-equivalent.
10	0.39	0.17

Discussion.

It will be observed from the above tables that with the exception of silver nitrate the adsorption of other metallic ions such as copper, barium, potassium and aluminium is decreased in presence of another adsorbable ion. These results are therefore in line with the results of other workers already mentioned. Thus with increasing concentration of either copper or barium in a solution containing a given amount of the other the adsorption of each is more and more diminished. The results are plotted in Figs. I and II. The case of silver, however, appears to be an interesting one and it seems probable that the adsorption complex of silver and manganese dioxide is a more stable one than others. Recently Pawlow (*Kolloid Zeit.*, 1924, 35, 375) has suggested that the adsorption of silver by manganese dioxide is a case of complicated chemical adsorption where silver reacts with $Mn(OH)_4$ yielding various salts of the type, $Mn(OH)_3AgO$, $Mn(OH)_2(AgO)_2$ etc., resulting in the liberation of free acid. It may be stated here that silver, though a monovalent ion, has a very high precipitating power on a manganese dioxide sol and it has been found in general that ions which have a great chemical affinity for a colloid usually possess a great precipitating power. The difference between the behaviour of silver and barium seems therefore to point that in the adsorption of silver the adsorptive forces approach more nearly those of primary valency forces.

Patrick and Barclay (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 1400) have found that in the replacement of alkali by means of silver, copper and ferric ions on a silica surface, equivalent amounts of sodium are replaced by each of the heavier ions. From our tables, however, it will be

FIG. I.

FIG. II.

apparent that the amount of adsorbed ion is never equivalent to the adsorption of the replaced ion. On the other hand the sum of the adsorption of two ions expressed in equivalents is always greater than the amount of adsorption of either of them at the same concentration when only one is present. Further, in the mixture potassium nitrate and barium nitrate it will be observed that though the adsorption of barium is decreased considerably in presence of potassium, yet at the same time the combined adsorption of potassium and barium is greater than either that of potassium or barium when each is present alone. Should this result be confirmed in the case of arsenious sulphide sol then we think that Weiser's explanation regarding the antagonistic action of potassium and barium ions remains no longer valid.* In Table VII the results of two experiments of this nature are summarised.

TABLE VII.

Cation	Original concentration in milli equivalent.	Adsorption separately.	Adsorption from mixture.	Sum.	Percentage decrease.
Ba ⁺⁺	10	1.126	0.99	} 1.16	12
K ⁺	10	0.39	0.17		30
Ba ⁺⁺	10	1.109	0.724	} 2.484	38
Cu ⁺⁺	12.16	1.96	1.76		9.9

* We may state here also that though potassium ion cuts down the adsorption of barium yet there is no antagonistic effect between these two salts in the case of manganese dioxide colloid. Hence simply the cutting down of the adsorption of one cation by another cannot be a sufficient explanation or a proof of the existence of cationic antagonism with As_2S_3 sol.

Another point of interest in Table VII is the percentage decrease of adsorption of one ion in the presence of another. Thus barium is much more adsorbed than potassium and along with it the decrease in the amount of adsorption of barium in presence of potassium is about twelve per cent., whereas under the same conditions the adsorption of potassium ion is decreased to the extent of about thirty per cent. In the case of the mixture, copper and barium, copper is much more adsorbed than barium and the percentage of the replacement of copper by barium is also much less than that of barium by copper. These results therefore support the general observation of many workers that the more adsorbable ions are less readily replaceable.

Mention may be made here of another fact which at first appeared to be puzzling. Thus in the adsorption of barium from a mixture of barium chloride and a low concentration aluminium nitrate, it was found that instead of decreasing, the adsorption actually increased to more than that from pure barium chloride. It was found out, however, that the presence of nitrate ion increases the amount of adsorption of barium ion by manganese dioxide. Similarly in presence of sulphate, adsorption of copper is increased from a solution of copper chloride. In Tables VIII and IX these data are shown. It will be observed that the anion has a very marked effect on the adsorption of the cation.

TABLE VIII.

Adsorption of Ba⁺⁺ from Ba(NO₃)₂ and BaCl₂.

Original concentration of Ba ⁺⁺ in milli-equivalents.	Adsorption of Ba ⁺⁺ in milli-equivalents.	
	Adsorption from BaCl ₂	Adsorption from Ba(NO ₃) ₂ .
20	1.366	1.43
15	1.255	1.40
10	1.109	1.126
5	0.827	0.952

TABLE IX.

Adsorption of Copper from CuSO₄ and CuCl₂.

Original concentration of CuSO ₄ in milli-equivalents.	Adsorption of Cu ⁺⁺ in milli-equivalents.	Original concentration of CuCl ₂ in milli-equivalents.	Adsorption of Cu ⁺⁺ in milli-equivalents.
25.5	3.20	24.32	2.42
20.4	3.14	18.24	2.24
15.3	2.88	12.16	1.96
10.2	2.54	6.08	1.65
5.1	1.99		

The reason for this behaviour is that sulphate ion has been found to be more adsorbed than chloride in the case of copper salts (*Cf. Sen, Biochem. Zeit., 1926, 169, 192*). It appears probable that nitrate ion is also more adsorbed than chloride in the case of barium salts. This result is thus similar to that of Weiser (*J. Phys. Chem., 1926, 30, 27*), who has recently found that barium is more adsorbed from barium ferrocyanide than from barium chloride by arsenious sulphide sol. Bancroft (*loc. cit.*) also cites

references about the effect of acid and alkali in increasing the amount of adsorption of acidic and basic dyes respectively.

In conclusion we may state that experiments are now in progress on the simultaneous adsorption of ions by arsenious sulphide, ferric hydroxide and aluminium hydroxide sols and also the coagulation of these sols and that of manganese dioxide by the same mixtures of electrolytes and hence a theoretical discussion on the relation between these two phenomena is postponed for the next communication.

Summary.

1. An experimental study has been made of the simultaneous adsorption of several pairs of metallic ions by hydrated manganese dioxide.

2. It has been found that the adsorbed silver cannot be replaced by either potassium or barium. Both potassium and barium can, however, be displaced one by the other. Copper and aluminium are also displaced by barium and *vice versa*.

3. In general, with increasing concentration of the replacing ion in solution more and more of the adsorbed ion is displaced.

4. It has been found that the ion which is more adsorbed is less readily replaced by a less adsorbable ion.

5. The cation is more adsorbed from a salt which contains a highly adsorbable anion.

6. The sum of the adsorption of two ions from a mixture is always greater than the adsorption of either of them when present alone in the solution.